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Journal Article**Author(s):**

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Publication date:

2025-08

Permanent link:

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-c-000786800>

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Originally published in:

The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology 139(7-8), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-025-16110-9>

Optimizing process parameters in manufacturing to reduce carbon footprint with contextual Bayesian optimization

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Received: 13 January 2025 / Accepted: 9 July 2025 / Published online: 17 July 2025
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Abstract

Reducing carbon emissions and achieving sustainability targets in manufacturing are crucial challenges. This study proposes the use of contextual Bayesian optimization (CBO) as a data-efficient method to optimize process parameters, specifically aiming to reduce the carbon footprint. The methodology is demonstrated using fused deposition modeling (FDM). The goal of this research is to develop and demonstrate an optimization framework that accounts for external factors—specifically, ambient temperature—in the optimization of process parameters such as nozzle temperature, infill percentage, and print speed. To model the relationship between inputs and outputs, a Gaussian process (GP) model is employed. The results show a 26% reduction in carbon footprint and a 22% cost saving, while still maintaining print quality. The study highlights the potential of CBO in sustainable manufacturing and outlines its applicability to other processes, such as turning, grinding, or milling.

Keywords Fused deposition · Additive manufacturing · CO₂ emission · Optimization · Bayesian optimization

Nomenclature

α	Overhang angle (°)
C	Carbon footprint (kg CO ₂)
C_E	Specific carbon footprint of electricity (kg CO ₂ /kWh)
C_m	Specific carbon footprint of material (kg CO ₂ /kg material)
d_l	Layer thickness (mm)
E	Energy used per manufacturing cycle (kWh)
k_M	Matérn 5/2 kernel
m_{mat}	Material used per manufacturing cycle (kg)
Q_c	Cooling fan speed (%)
Q_i	Infill percentage (%)
Q_s	Stringing parameter
R_a	Arithmetic average roughness (μm)
T_a	Ambient temperature (°C)
T_b	Heat bed temperature (°C)
T_n	Nozzle temperature (°C)

v_p Print speed (mm/s)

1 Introduction

As the global focus shifts towards sustainable manufacturing practices and the push for net-zero carbon emissions intensifies, for example, with the UN Paris Agreement [1], the EU Green Deal [2], or the long-term Swiss federal climate strategy [3], attention has increasingly been drawn to the environmental impact of such manufacturing practices. To meet stringent environmental goals, companies and nations must focus on understanding and mitigating the carbon footprint of manufacturing processes.

In response to the increased focus on low-carbon manufacturing policies, Li et al. [4] introduced an energy dataspace model for discrete manufacturing that enables in-process carbon footprint estimation using structured sensor data. Katchasuwanmanee et al. [5] introduced the e-ProMan system, a big data-driven energy management platform that optimizes energy use in manufacturing by integrating weather forecasts, ambient sensors, machine energy consumption, production processes, and production schedules. These works underscore the growing importance of context-aware data-informed systems in driving sustainable manufacturing outcomes.

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Additive manufacturing, including prevalent methods such as selective laser melting (SLM) [6] or fused deposition modelling (FDM) [7], holds promise for minimizing waste and energy consumption through more efficient material usage and targeted optimization. While FDM is widely recognized for its versatility and cost-effectiveness in producing complex geometries [8], its environmental impact must also be addressed. By enhancing energy efficiency and reducing material waste, additive manufacturing can play an important role in achieving carbon reduction targets, making it an attractive area for sustainability-driven innovation across industries.

Previous studies have already explored these concerns and ideas, and it has been shown that FDM has a high specific energy consumption of over 500 MJ/kg deposited material with regard to other AM methods that can reach well below 100 MJ/kg [9], which may imply greater potential carbon footprint reduction for FDM.

The energy consumption of the printing process, combined with the type and quantity of material used, directly contributes to the overall environmental impact of FDM [10]. Optimizing critical process parameters, such as nozzle temperature, print speed, and infill percentage, offers a pathway to reduce both energy usage and material waste, thereby lowering the overall carbon footprint.

However, finding the ideal balance between these parameters is a complex challenge [11]. The task becomes even more complex as variables such as filament type, machine performance, and environmental conditions fluctuate, complicating the search for optimal, sustainable settings.

In response to this challenge, contextual Bayesian optimization (CBO) [12] presents a promising solution by incorporating external context factors, for example, ambient temperature, into the optimization process. Context parameters are parameters that, although they influence the output of the model, cannot be specifically chosen. For example, lower ambient temperatures may cause an FDM printer to use more energy to heat up the nozzle and heat bed, increasing its carbon footprint. While the optimization problem is formulated identically to conventional, non-contextual optimization approaches, CBO dynamically adapts to different operational context parameters. This adaptability is desirable in minimizing energy and material consumption, the key contributors to the carbon footprint of the FDM process.

As such, this work provides a new perspective on sustainability-driven optimization in additive manufacturing, aiming to reduce energy consumption and material use while maintaining or improving production quality. The inclusion of contextual environmental factors allows for an optimization process that is more flexible and responsive to changing operational conditions.

The optimization of process parameters for FDM has been done in the past in multiple studies, such as [11], where

Dey and Yodo systematically reviewed different optimization strategies both for single-objective optimization and multi-objective optimization.

Another study, by Sharma et al. [13], used the Taguchi method to optimize mechanical properties such as tensile strength and compressive strength of ABS test specimens.

The work of Camposeco-Negrete [14] also used the Taguchi methodology to improve FDM part quality and process sustainability.

In contrast, the work of Al-Ghamdi [15] used an iterative approach, with incremental changes and improvements to the desirability function, to find the optimal FDM process parameters with regard to both energy and material consumption.

If we take a step back and look at the use of optimization in other manufacturing methods, the work by Maier et al. [16] utilizes Bayesian optimization to select and optimize the process parameters for turning.

Zhang et al. [17] used a multi-objective optimization to improve both the efficiency of CNC milling and reduce carbon emissions of the manufacturing process.

However, contextual Bayesian optimization has not been explored to reduce carbon emissions in manufacturing. Due to the lack of research in this area, this paper introduces the application of CBO to optimize manufacturing process parameters, specifically targeting carbon footprint reduction. Specifically, we aim to improve process parameters in FDM printing. Through the integration of contextual information into the optimization framework, this approach seeks to strike a balance between achieving high print quality and meeting sustainability objectives.

By addressing the challenge of multi-dimensional optimization with contextual awareness, this research offers a novel and practical approach to minimizing the environmental impact of FDM, advancing both the pursuit of greener production methods and the field of additive manufacturing.

2 Methodology

2.1 Contextual Bayesian optimization

Bayesian optimization (BO), as reviewed in [18], is a method used to optimize expensive-to-evaluate black-box functions, typically utilizing a probabilistic model like a Gaussian process (GP) to predict an objective function and guide exploration and exploitation in the search space. In this work, contextual Bayesian optimization (CBO) [12] is applied, enabling optimization in settings where additional contextual information is available. Here, the context refers to environmental factors, specifically ambient temperature in the case of FDM, but it could also encompass other variables such as tool wear.

In CBO, the goal is to learn the mapping from both process variables and contextual variables to the output variables (objective and constraint variables). This is done by jointly modeling the relationship between:

- Controllable process parameters: nozzle temperature T_n , bed temperature T_b , print speed v_p , layer thickness d_l , cooling fan speed Q_c , and infill percentage Q_i
- Contextual variable: ambient temperature T_a
- Objective variables: carbon footprint, which consists of energy consumption E and material usage m_{mat}
- Constraint variables: overhang angle α , surface roughness R_a , and stringing parameter Q_s

GP models, and consequently CBO, were selected over conventional optimization approaches due to their ability to handle data-scarce scenarios. GP models are particularly well-suited for applications where only a small number of observations are available. In contrast to other approaches, such as neural networks, GP models not only provide point estimates but also offer quantification of uncertainty. This includes uncertainty arising from sparse data, which increases in regions farther away from the observed samples. This property not only allows the optimization to select new sample points efficiently but also contributes to a more comprehensive and interpretable model.

2.2 Gaussian process (GP) models

To model the objective function, a Gaussian process (GP), as described in detail in [19], is used. This non-parametric model provides predictions of the objective function, along with an uncertainty measure for these predictions. A GP is defined by a mean function $m(x)$ and a covariance function, typically called a kernel [20]. In this study, the kernel used is the Matérn 5/2 kernel k_M , found in [19]

$$k_M(r) = \sigma_f^2 \exp(-\sqrt{5}r) \left(1 + \sqrt{5}r + \frac{5}{3}r^2\right) \tag{1}$$

where σ_f^2 is the signal variance, and r is the Euclidean distance between two points \underline{x} and \underline{x}' in n dimensions, which is calculated as [21, 22]

$$r(\underline{x}, \underline{x}') = \sqrt{(\underline{x} - \underline{x}')^T \underline{P}(\underline{x} - \underline{x}')} \tag{2}$$

$$\underline{P} = \text{diag}(l_1^{-2}, l_2^{-2}, \dots, l_n^{-2}) \tag{3}$$

where \underline{P} is a diagonal matrix containing the inverted characteristic length scale parameters l_i^{-2} . In this case, x is a point in the process parameter space, which encodes the chosen n different process parameters. The posterior mean μ_t and the

posterior variance σ_t^2 of the GP model can be calculated, at any point \underline{x}_* , following [19, 22]:

$$\mu_t(\underline{x}_*) = m(\underline{x}_*) + \underline{k}^T \left(\underline{K} + \sigma_N^2 \underline{I}\right)^{-1} \left(\underline{y}_t - \underline{m}(\underline{x}_{1t})\right) \tag{4}$$

$$\sigma_t^2(\underline{x}_*) = k(\underline{x}_*, \underline{x}_*) - \underline{k}^T(\underline{x}_*) \left(\underline{K} + \sigma_N^2 \underline{I}\right)^{-1}(\underline{x}_*) \tag{5}$$

Here, \underline{I} denotes the identity matrix, \underline{y}_t are t observed outputs, and the prior mean function vector is represented by $\underline{m}(\underline{x}_{1t}) = [m(x_1) \dots, (x_t)]^T$. The term σ_N^2 refers to the variance of the signal noise, which is assumed to follow a Gaussian distribution. Additionally, $\underline{k}(\underline{x}_*) = [k(\underline{x}_*, \underline{x}_1) \dots k(\underline{x}_*, \underline{x}_t)]^T$ is the covariance vector.

The covariance matrix \underline{K} is defined as [19]

$$\underline{K} = \begin{bmatrix} k(x_1, x_2) & \dots & k(x_1, x_2) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ k(x_1, x_2) & \dots & k(x_1, x_2) \end{bmatrix} \tag{6}$$

Gaussian process models use hyperparameters such as the output scale (signal variance σ_f), the input scale (length scales l_i), and the signal noise σ_N , which can be selected based on prior knowledge. However, such prior knowledge is often unavailable. An alternative approach is to define priors for the hyperparameters, referred to as hyperpriors. If precise prior knowledge is available, priors with a narrow expectation range can be chosen; otherwise, broader expectation ranges for the hyperpriors are typically more appropriate to cover a larger range of possibilities.

In this work, the BoTorch framework [23] was used for the Gaussian process model and Bayesian optimization. The default hyperpriors provided by BoTorch are adopted. Specifically, the length scale and output scale parameters were assigned gamma-distributed priors. The gamma distribution is a probability density function defined as [24]

$$f(x) = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} x^{\alpha-1} e^{-\beta x} \tag{7}$$

where α is the shape parameter, β is the rate parameter, and Γ is the gamma function. Some random variable x that is gamma-distributed with the shape parameter α and rate parameter β is written as $x \sim \Gamma(\alpha, \beta) \equiv \text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$. As seen in Fig. 1, the length scale uses a Gamma(3, 6) and the output scale uses a Gamma(2, 0.15) distribution. These hyperparameters correspond to a scaled space, where inputs were normalized to the range [0,1] and outputs were standardized to have zero mean and unit variance.

The selection of these hyperpriors provides distinct advantages and disadvantages. If we use a broad prior on the output scale, the model is provided with the flexibility to capture data points that vary widely. Similarly, a short length scale allows

Fig. 1 Gamma(3, 6) prior for length scale (top). Gamma(2, 0.15) prior for output scale (bottom)

the model to represent sharp changes between neighboring points precisely. However, these choices also introduce additional uncertainty: the short length scale increases uncertainty around unobserved regions, while the large output scale prior adds additional variance, further increasing the overall model uncertainty.

Overall, this selection of hyperpriors makes the model more robust when dealing with complex objective functions with many peaks and valleys. It also reduces the risk of the model getting “stuck” in local optima, increasing the likelihood of finding the global optimum. The trade-off, however, is an overall increase in uncertainty and a bias towards exploration over exploitation in the model’s decision-making process.

The determination and optimization of these hyperparameters to best match the observed data often occur through maximum likelihood estimation [25]. Here, the exact marginal log likelihood [19],

$$\log p(\underline{y}|\underline{X}, \theta) = -\frac{1}{2}\underline{y}^T(\underline{K} + \sigma_N^2\underline{I})^{-1}\underline{y} - \frac{1}{2}\log|\underline{K} + \sigma_N^2\underline{I}| - \frac{n}{2}\log 2\pi \quad (8)$$

gets used, \underline{y} are the observed outputs, \underline{X} the observed input points, \underline{K} is the covariance matrix evaluated at the observed points, θ represents the hyperparameters of the kernel, and n is the number of observations. By maximizing the likelihood with respect to θ , a set of hyperparameters that best describe the observed data is obtained.

2.3 Acquisition function

As for the utilized acquisition function, the logarithmic expected improvement (LogEI) acquisition function was employed to guide the search for optimal solutions, which is, according to [26], defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \log_e(a_{EI}(x)) &= \log_e(\mathbb{E}[\max(f(\underline{x}_*) - f_{best}), 0]) \\ &= \log_e\left(\sigma(\underline{x}_*)h\left(\frac{\mu(\underline{x}_*) - f_{best}}{\sigma(\underline{x}_*)}\right)\right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

with $\mu(\underline{x}_*)$ being the predicted mean and $\sigma(\underline{x}_*)$ the standard deviation at point \underline{x}_* , f_{best} as the currently best observed value of the observation loop, $h(z) = \phi(z) + z\Phi(z)$ with the standard normal distribution ϕ and standard normal cumulative distribution Φ respectively, and \mathbb{E} the expected value.

As an acquisition function of the expected improvement (EI) family, the function inherently balances exploration and exploitation by considering both the predicted value of a candidate and its probability of occurring. The LogEI function over regular EI is chosen, as in previous research [26], which has shown that LogEI offers several benefits in terms of computational and numerical stability, as well as performance. Notably, the standard EI function can sometimes result in overflow errors, even when using double-precision floating-point arithmetic, an issue mitigated by LogEI.

The optimization is subject to certain constraints, such as maintaining surface roughness below a predefined threshold or ensuring mechanical integrity for a minimum degree of overhang, for example. These constraints are enforced throughout the optimization process to ensure that the optimized settings result in functional and high-quality prints.

Due to the set constraints, the acquisition function without constraints is then multiplied by the probability of fulfilling the boundary conditions as demonstrated in [27]

$$a_{cLogEI}(x) = a_{LogEI}(x) \cdot P_1(x) \cdot P_2(x) \cdot \dots \cdot P_n(x) \quad (10)$$

With a_{cLogEI} being the value of the constrained logarithmic expected improvement, and $P_1(x) \cdot P_2(x) \cdot \dots \cdot P_n(x)$ being the probabilities that a point \underline{x} in the process parameter space fulfills the n different boundary conditions.

2.4 Implementation

2.4.1 Optimization

The optimization objective in this paper is to find the optimal process parameters \underline{x}_{min} , which minimize carbon footprint while fulfilling quality constraints:

$$\underline{x}_{min} = \arg \min(E * C_E + m_{mat} * C_m) \quad (11)$$

Subject to:

$$(\alpha \geq 50^\circ) \quad (12)$$

$$(R_a \leq 15\mu m) \quad (13)$$

$$(Q_S \leq 4) \quad (14)$$

Table 1 Process parameters and allowed bounded values for optimization

Process parameters	T_{nozzle} (°C)	T_{bed} (°C)	v_{print} (mm/s)	d_{layer} (mm)	Q_{cool} (%)	Q_{infill} (%)
Lower bound	210	50	20	0.05	0	0
Upper bound	275	100	150	0.3	100	100

Specifically, (11) is the mathematical model of the carbon footprint C that is to be optimized, whereas (12–14) are the applied constraints on the outputs. C_E is the carbon footprint per kWh electric energy (given by [28] as 128 g CO₂/kWh) and C_m the carbon footprint per kg of material used (given by [29] as 5.85 kg CO₂/kg PETG). Consequently, E is the measured energy consumption, and m_{mat} is the amount of material used during the manufacturing of the test sample. As for the inequality constraints, α is the overhang angle, R_a is the arithmetic average roughness, and Q_S is the stringing parameter.

Fig. 2 Flowchart visualizing the implementation of the optimization. The loop continues until the stopping criterion (20 iterations) is met, after which the final solution is selected

As for the constraints set on the process parameters (model inputs x), Table 1 visualizes the minimum and maximum values these parameters were allowed to reach. T_n and T_b are the values for the temperature of the extrusion nozzle and heat bed, respectively. v_p is the print speed, and d_l the layer thickness. The last two parameters, Q_c and Q_i , are dimensionless values: Q_i being the infill percentage, which is the ratio of solid material to empty space inside the printed model, and Q_c being the cooling fan speed given as a percentage.

Figure 2 illustrates the main optimization loop. First, the model is trained with a small set of initial data, consisting of both the input variables (which are the process parameters defined in Table 1, carbon footprint C and the boundary conditions α_{max} , R_a , Q_s) and contextual variables, which in this case is the ambient temperature T_a . A GP model is then created, fitted, and subsequently evaluated. If a predefined stopping criterion is met, the optimization ends; otherwise, the loop continues. The stopping criterion was defined as 20 loop iterations completed; more complex stopping criteria can, however, be defined, as outlined in [22]. The code generates as output a new set of candidate process parameters by optimizing the acquisition function, in this case minimizing (11), which is then subsequently experimentally evaluated. This new data is added to the existing dataset, and the GP model is updated, restarting the entire loop.

2.4.2 Experimental evaluation and data collection

The maximum possible overhang angle, α_{max} , was measured using a printed, smooth arc with a progressively increasing angle (see Fig. 3, right). The arc was designed to include a maximum angle of 80° , pushing the limit of the ability to print unsupported structures. During testing, the angle at which the print failed (defined as the failure angle α_{max}) was recorded. Failure was defined as the point at which the printed layers could no longer maintain their structural integrity, resulting in deformations of the structure or a collapse of the overhang.

Surface roughness R_a was measured using MarSurf PS1 and following ISO 21920-3 [30]. The measurements were

Fig. 3 Surface roughness sample (left). Combined overhang and stringing sample, modified from [31] (right). The arc on the left of the sample is used to measure α_{max} , and the tower on the right is used to determine Q_s

conducted in the direction perpendicular to the layers of the test sample, in this case along the z -axis of the left sample as seen in Fig. 3. Due to the nature of FDM printing, this axis faces the greatest challenges in achieving a smooth finish, primarily because of the layer lines caused by the layer-by-layer nature of this manufacturing technology.

Finally, stringing, another common issue in FDM printing, was evaluated. Stringing, also known as oozing, occurs when the extruder moves from one point to another while material leaks from the nozzle [32]. It appears as thin, unwanted strands of filament, often appearing between different parts of the print, although in more severe cases, the thin wisps of filament can become quite thick. This can impact product quality and be influenced by ambient temperature, as well as multiple different process parameters [33]. To quantify stringing, a grading scale was created, which gave a grade Q_s ranging from 1 to 7. On this scale, a lower grade indicated fewer stringing defects, while a higher grade corresponded to more severe stringing defects between features. Each print was graded based on the extent and severity of stringing observed, with those exhibiting minimal stringing awarded a lower grade, reflecting better print quality.

3 Results

3.1 Optimization

As illustrated in Fig. 4, the optimization process based on CBO reduced the calculated carbon footprint of the FDM process by 26%. A detailed comparison of the optimal process parameters before and after optimization is provided in Table 2. Several key adjustments were made during the optimization.

Notably, parameters such as bed temperature, nozzle temperature, print speed, and infill percentage were reduced when compared to the initial, unoptimized values. The reduction in nozzle and bed temperatures likely contributed to lower energy consumption during the printing process.

Fig. 4 Expected improvement value a_{EI} and optimization plot for current best value

Similarly, the decrease in infill percentage reduced material usage, further contributing to a lower carbon footprint.

In contrast, other parameters, such as layer thickness and cooling fan speed, increased at the end of the optimization cycle, as shown in Table 2. The increase in layer thickness suggests that a coarser resolution, while detrimental to surface finish, expedited print time, thereby reducing overall energy consumption. These findings align with those from a previous study [15], which found that increased layer thickness and reduced fill rate were associated with lower energy consumption. The constraint set by equation (13) does, however, limit the maximum layer thickness before the surface becomes too rough, as in our measurements, surface roughness rose proportionally to layer height. A measured surface roughness of $14.93 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{m}$ at 0.18mm layer thickness for the best measured point thus suggests that this layer thickness is the maximum before the constraint kicks in. The increased cooling fan speed Q_c in Table 2 likely indicates the need for quicker solidification at higher layer thicknesses. These parameter shifts highlight the complex trade-offs involved in optimizing for sustainability while maintaining part performance.

3.2 Model comparison

Figure 5 presents a comparison between the contextual model (depicted by the blue line with gray uncertainty area) and a non-contextual, standard model (represented by the red line with light red uncertainty area). As observed, the inclusion of ambient temperature as a contextual input enables the model to adjust its predictions in response to varying environmental conditions dynamically. Specifically, the contextual model predicts a higher carbon footprint at lower ambient

temperatures. This behavior aligns with the intuitive increase in energy demand for maintaining stable processing temperatures in colder environments. Conversely, at higher ambient temperatures, the contextual model predicts a lower carbon footprint than the other model.

In contrast, the non-contextual model, by definition, lacks any parameters that account for ambient temperature or similar external factors. As a result, its predictions remain constant throughout the entire context space, regardless of fluctuations in environmental conditions.

Furthermore, Fig. 5 includes model validation samples, represented by yellow dots, which provide a direct comparison between the predicted values and actual data. As clearly illustrated, the contextual model not only aligns better with the validation data but also makes more accurate predictions across the entire ambient temperature range. This is particularly evident in regions of both lower and higher ambient temperatures, where the non-contextual model deviates significantly from the observed data, with the deviation being especially pronounced for temperatures below $18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The improved predictive accuracy of the contextual model suggests that incorporating environmental context is crucial for developing reliable models in scenarios where external conditions vary significantly.

While the tested validation samples follow the predicted mean rather closely, as seen earlier in Fig. 5, a relatively large confidence interval exists, especially when compared to the samples. To further explore this, the contributions to uncertainty from aleatoric uncertainty and epistemic uncertainty are investigated. Aleatoric uncertainty is the uncertainty from randomness, while epistemic uncertainty is the uncertainty due to missing data. This is more clearly visualized in Fig. 6: The 95% confidence interval for the measurement noise (aleatoric uncertainty) is approximately 1.02 g CO_2 , while the model uncertainty averages around 6.04 g CO_2 . This difference arises because the smaller uncertainty reflects aleatoric uncertainty, whereas the larger value accounts for both aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties. As previously discussed in the methodology, this is not unexpected due to the default hyperpriors that BoTorch [23] uses, specifically for the output scale and the length scale.

To validate the assumption of normality for the data distribution, the Shapiro-Wilk test [34] was employed. This statistical test is particularly suitable for the small dataset of only six samples, taken at the same optimal process parameters as seen in Table 2 and ambient temperature $(24.85 \pm 0.53$

Table 2 Optimal measured process parameters

Process Parameters	T_{nozzle} (°C)	T_{bed} (°C)	v_{print} (mm/s)	d_{layer} (mm)	Q_{cool} (%)	Q_{infill} (%)
Optimal value	228	66	58	0.18	52	9
Beginning value	243	92	65	0.17	36	30

Fig. 5 Carbon footprint as a function of ambient temperature, comparing contextual BO with regular BO. Process parameters are left unchanged for comparison

°C). The computed test statistic was $W(6) = 0.959$, which exceeded the critical value $W^*(6) = 0.7777$ and thus fell within the 95% region of acceptance. The p -value equals 0.9322, which is quite large, indicating no statistically significant difference between the sample data and a normal distribution. This result supports the assumption that the measurement noise σ_N^2 in the Gaussian process model is normally distributed. The $Q-Q$ plot, as seen in Fig. 7, graphically visualizes this.

3.3 Economic implications of the optimization

Finally, during this study, an unintended but interesting finding was made: reducing the carbon footprint also resulted in lower manufacturing costs. The optimization process reduced costs by 22.2%, from 0.36 CHF to 0.28 CHF per sample pair (one of each in Fig. 2). This result demonstrates the economic feasibility of sustainable practices and highlights that sustainability efforts can yield financial benefits. It

Fig. 6 Aleatoric vs epistemic uncertainty. Aleatoric measurement uncertainty visualized in green

Fig. 7 $Q-Q$ plot of the calculated carbon footprint

demonstrates that companies can reduce their environmental impact without incurring additional costs, thereby aligning economic and environmental goals for a more sustainable and competitive manufacturing approach.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, the application of contextual Bayesian optimization (CBO) is explored for optimizing key process parameters in manufacturing, specifically for FDM 3D printing, with the explicit goal of reducing the carbon footprint. By incorporating ambient temperature as contextual information, the approach allowed for adaptive parameter tuning. The results of experiments demonstrated that CBO effectively reduced energy consumption and material usage, both of which are major contributors to the overall carbon footprint of the FDM process.

The process parameters, including but not limited to infill percentage, print speed, and bed temperature, could be optimized within the context to balance sustainability objectives with print quality. The application of CBO led to a significant reduction in carbon footprint of 26%, particularly by optimizing bed temperature, and a decrease in material waste, which was the primary contributor to a cost reduction of 22%, all while maintaining print integrity and quality.

This research highlights the potential of CBO as a powerful tool for sustainable manufacturing processes. Overall, it presents a viable path toward reducing the environmental impact of manufacturing processes without compromising operational efficiency or product quality. For future research, we recommend applying the CBO optimization framework to other manufacturing processes such as turning or milling. Furthermore, we suggest including additional contextual variables beyond ambient temperature, such as tool wear.

Author contribution Matteo C. Vincent: methodology, software, investigation, writing—original draft. Markus Maier: conceptualization, methodology, writing—review and editing. Konrad Wegener: funding acquisition, writing—review and editing.

Funding This study is part of the MARS project funded by Horizon Europe (Number 101091783) and by the State Secretariat, Research and Innovation SERI, Switzerland (Number 22.00557).

Declarations

Conflict of interest The authors declare no competing interests.

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